

**DAMAGE PROPAGATION DURING FLEXURAL AND AXIAL
FATIGUE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL KEVLAR FABRIC
REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITES**

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ABSTRACT

The paper describes results of the flexural and axial fatigue investigations on a Kevlar fiber reinforced epoxy composite with emphasis on damage growth. A damage law has been found for flexural and axial fatigue cases. The damage law fits well to the experimental results. It was found that damage propagates in three stages, namely damage initiation stage, steady damage stage and damage propagation stage. The S-N curves have been represented by linear law and power law between normalized fatigue stress and log of fatigue life. The scatter in fatigue data has been analysed by a two parameter Weibull distribution and probability S-N curves have been drawn.

INTRODUCTION

Fatigue behaviour of Kevlar composites has attracted much less attention of the researchers than the glass and graphite fiber composites have. Kevlar fiber composites are nowadays, being increasingly used due to their light weight, high strength and high modulus.

Damage in composite laminates consists of the development and accumulation of numerous defects. The present paper discusses the way damage propagates with number of cycles during flexural and axial fatigue loading and also analyses the scatter in fatigue life data.

TEST SPECIMENS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The material used for present investigations is Kevlar-49 fabric reinforced epoxy composite. Kevlar-49 fabric with unidirectional construction has fibers approximately ten times in the warp direction than those in the fill direction. The composite laminates (3mm thick) were cast in the laboratory using hand-lay-up technique. The composite laminates used for flexural fatigue tests had a fiber volume fraction of about 44% whereas for axial fatigue tests, fiber volume fraction was 52%.

Flexural fatigue tests were conducted on 167 mm long, 12.7 mm wide and 3 mm thick specimens. One end of the specimens was fixed while the other end was cycled between known transverse displacement limits with zero mean displacement in an indigenously developed fatigue machine. The point of load application was located 115 mm away from the fixed end. The displacement limits were 12, 13, 18, 21 and 26 mm so that fatigue life varied between 10^3 and 5×10^5 cycles. Bending moment at the fixed end of the specimen was measured by means of a especially designed and fabricated dynamometer and recorded at desire intervals through a visicorder without interrupting fatigue tests so that the progressive fatigue damage may be easily studied.

A careful attention was paid to the design of the specimen for axial fatigue tests. Rectangular and dogbone specimens with different sizes and shapes were used with different sizes of end tabs. After several trials, rectangular specimen of length 150 mm and width 14 mm selected with end tabs of length 42 mm and thickness 1.5 mm. The material used for tab was glass fabric/epoxy composite, with epoxy as adhesive. The specimen finally selected failed in the gage section without debonding of end tabs.

Axial fatigue tests were conducted on an MTS servohydraulic testing system. All the tests were performed in tension - tension mode with stress ratio R equal to 0.1. These tests were conducted in haversine mode under load control. Nearly 65 specimens were tested. Maximum stress in fatigue cycles was 90, 85, 80, 70, 65, 60, and 50 percent, respectively of the average ultimate static strength. These stress levels were selected so as to vary the fatigue life from 100 cycles to half million cycles. For 90% and 85% stress levels, frequency was kept at 1 Hz while for 80%, 70% and 65% stress levels it was 3 Hz and for 60 and 50% stress levels it was 6 Hz.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. S-N Curve

The S-N curves from flexural and axial fatigue test results are shown in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. In the range of stress amplitude and fatigue life studied, the S-N curve may be approximated by a linear law or a power law between normalized stress and logarithm of cyclic life as follows,

$$S_{\max}/S_u = m \log_{10} n_f + 1 \quad (1)$$

$$(S_{\max}/S_u) N_f^a = b \quad (2)$$

Where m , 1 , a and b are constants. S_u is the average ultimate tensile strength of the material and S_{\max} is the maximum stress applied during the test. The values of constants are given in the figures for each case.

The linear law appears to fit the experimental data better. The flexural and axial fatigue strength as calculated from linear law at $N = 10^6$ is about $0.258 S_u$ and $0.489 S_u$ respectively with no indication of an apparent endurance limit.

2. P-S-N Curve

The scatter in fatigue life data has been analyzed through the following a two parameter Weibull distribution function:

$$P = \exp [-(N_{f \text{ nor}} / \beta)^{\alpha}] \quad (3)$$

$$N_{f \text{ nor}} = N_f / N_{f \text{ th}} \quad (4)$$

Where, P is probability of survival, $N_{f \text{ th}}$ is theoretical fatigue life predicted from linear law, α shape parameter and β scale parameter. The parameters have been evaluated by pooling the normalized fatigue data. The theoretical probability distribution curves are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. They are found to fit quite well with experimental points. The curves for 90% and 10% probability of survival are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig.1 Stress fatigue life curve for flexural fatigue.

Fig.2 Stress fatigue life curve for axial fatigue.

Fig.3 Cumulative probability distribution curve for flexural fatigue (symbols are same as in Fig.1)

Fig.4 Cumulative Probability distribution curve for axial fatigue.

3. Damage Model Development

A number of methods have been used by different investigators to identify and characterize the internal damage. Among them change in structural properties such as static or dynamic modulus, residual strength, stress, strain or temperature during fatigue loading are also considered indicative of internal damage.

The failure criterion applied is an important consideration to terminate the fatigue tests for composites. Several failure criteria have been used in fatigue studies by different investigators. Hahn and Kim¹ considered the failure occurs when the fatigue secant modulus (ratio of maximum stress and strain) reduces to the static secant modulus at failure.

This criterion of failure is found most suitable for flexural tests, where stroke controlled mode of loading is applied. Thus this criterion of failure^{1,2} of the specimen is selected for defining failure during present flexural fatigue tests. Reduction in the secant modulus has been taken as a measure of fatigue damage.³ It has been reported^{4,5} that Young's modulus is not particularly a good damage parameter for KFRP in axial fatigue loading because Young's modulus increases with no. of cycles for this material. For the development of a damage model in axial fatigue, fatigue modulus^{6,7} is taken as a damage parameter, which decreases continuously with fatigue cycling. Fatigue modulus was found till the complete separation of specimen. Fatigue modulus is defined as the slope of the plot of applied stress vs. resultant strain at a specific cycle. Fig.5 shows schematic diagram of stress-strain curve during cyclic loading. Due to the degradation of composite materials, stress-strain curve changes as the material is cycled continuously. In Fig. 5 fatigue modulus $F(N)$ at N^{th} cycle is represented by the slope of the line AN between applied stress and resultant strain at N^{th} cycle. Therefore,

$$F(N) = S_{\text{max}} / \epsilon (N) \quad (5)$$

Where S_{max} is max. stress applied during fatigue cycling and $\epsilon (N)$ is resultant strain at N^{th} cycle.

For the purpose of developing a damage law, normalized fatigue damage, D , has been defined for both cases such that D varies between 0 and 1.

For flexural fatigue:

$$D = \frac{E_f(1) - F_f(N)}{E_f(1) - E_f(N_f)} \quad (6)$$

Where, $E_f(1)$, $E_f(N)$ and $E_f(N_f)$ are the secant moduli at 1, N and N_f number of cycles respectively with N_f being the fatigue life of specimen.

For axial fatigue:

$$D = \frac{F(1)-F(N)}{F(1)-F(N_f)} \quad (7)$$

Where $F(1)$, $F(N)$ and $F(N_f)$ are the fatigue moduli at 1, N and N_f no. of cycles, respectively.

The number of cycles have also been normalized to vary between 0 and 1 as follows:

$$N^* = \frac{N - 1}{N_f - 1} \quad (8)$$

Progressive fatigue damage during flexural fatigue tests has been studied at all five different displacement limits indicated above whereas for axial fatigue at 90, 80, 70 and 60 percent stress levels. It is observed that the damage to the specimen during fatigue cycle is progressive and depends upon stress level and number of cycles. Some typical damage growth curves for flexural and axial fatigue are shown in Figs. 6-8. It may be observed that the curves shown may be divided into three parts with each part representing a distinct stage of damage accumulation. In stage I, damage initiates and accumulates at progressively lower growth rates, until the damage growth rate is nearly zero. This stage is referred to as the damage initiation stage. In stage II, the damage growth rate is nearly zero and thus, it is the steady damage stage. In stage III, the

damage starts increasing again, probably after a threshold damage is reached. In this stage the damage growth rate increases with the number of cycles and eventually leads to the specimen failure. This stage is called the damage propagation stage.

Fig.5 Schematic representation of fatigue modulus.

Fig.6 Damage accumulation plots for flexural fatigue (each symbol represents a specimen).

Fig.7 Damage accumulation plots for flexural fatigue (each symbol represents a specimen).

Fig.8 Damage accumulation plots for axial fatigue (each symbol represents a specimen).

It is observed that the level of damage and duration (number of cycles) of each stage depend upon the applied stress. At higher stress level, stage I continues for a large number of cycles and the damage level achieved is higher, the duration of steady damage and damage propagation stages are small. In stage III damage suddenly increases and failure occurs.

The following damage law has been found to represent the above damage behaviour,

$$D = \frac{A(e^{c_1 N^*} - 1)}{e^{c_1} - 1} + (1-A) \left(1 - \frac{e^{c_2(1-N^*)} - 1}{e^{c_2} - 1} \right) \quad (9)$$

Where, A, c1 and c2 are positive constants.

It may be noted that the first term on RHS of Equation 9 represents an increasing growth rate (stage III) and the second term a decreasing rate (stage I). Figures 6-8 also shows that the above damage law fits well with the experimental data.

CONCLUSIONS

- A. Strength of the material decreases with increase in number of cycles. The strength of the material at 10^6 cycles was found to be $0.258 S_u$ for flexural fatigue and $0.489 S_u$ for axial fatigue.
- B. For scatter analysis of fatigue life data, two parameter Weibull distribution function is suitable.
- C. The accumulation of damage of Kevlar fabric reinforced epoxy composite during flexural and axial fatigue can be divided into three stages, the damage initiation, steady damage and the damage propagation. Although the damage accumulation depends on fatigue stress or strain, it follows a definite trend.
- D. A numerical relation is developed to predict the damage propagation.

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REFERENCES

1. Hahn HT and Kim, J. Composite material, 10(1976), 156.
2. Brien O et. al., J. of composite material, 15(1981), 55.
3. Bhushan B, M.Tech. thesis, I.I.T.Kanpur, India (1987).
4. Mazumdar SK, M.Tech. thesis, I.I.T.Kanpur, India (1988).
5. Ganczakowski HL et. al., ICCM and ECCM, 3, Elsevier Applied Science Publishers Ltd. (1987), 3.16.
6. Hwang W and Han KS, J. Comp. Mat., 20(1986), 154.
7. Hwang W and Han KS, J. Comp. Mat., 20(1986), 125.